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THE FUNCTIONALITY OF SYMBOL AND ARTISTIC MINUTIAE IN AZERBAIJANI POETRY OF THE 1920s-1960s

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ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОСТЬ СИМВОЛА И ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ДЕТАЛЕЙ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОЙ ПОЭЗИИ 1920-60-Х ГОДОВ

Abstract.

This article discusses the relationship between symbols and artistic details in literary texts. Among the various types of artistic details, the function of symbolic details, the transformation of artistic details through various stages into artistic images, their symbolization, and other related matters are analyzed and supported with scientific and theoretical evidence. The use of symbolic details in Azerbaijani poetry of the 1920s-1960s, the symbolic function of details, the stages of symbolization of artistic details, and related issues are examined. While discussing the connection between detail and minutiae, as well as detail and symbol, it is emphasized that artistic detail is fundamental in the creation and understanding of symbols. Furthermore, the article analyzes how a detail selected in the context of psychological and philosophical typification in a literary text is subjected to a specific idea, associatively and symbolically transformed, and the advantages of symbolic details are explained. The new qualities that a detail gains after becoming symbolic are examined and supported with examples.

Аннотация.

В статье рассматриваются связи символа и художественной детали в литературном тексте. Функция символической детали среди различных типов художественной детали, превращение художественной детали через различные этапы в художественный образ, ее символизация и другие вопросы анализируются и обоснованы научно-теоретическими доказательствами. Изучаются использование символической детали в азербайджанской поэзии 1920-60-х годов, символическая функция детали, этапы символизации художественной детали и другие вопросы. При обсуждении связи между деталью и подробностью, а также деталью и символом подчеркивается, что художественная деталь играет основную роль в возникновении и восприятии символа. Кроме того, в статье анализируется, как выбранная в контексте психологической и философской типизации деталь подчиняется определенной идее, ассоциируется и символизируется, рассматриваются преимущества символической детали, а также новые качества, которые деталь приобретает после символизации, что обосновано приведенными примерами.

Keywords: *poetry, symbol, artistic minutiae, artistic image, detail*

Ключевые слова: *стих, символ, художественная деталь, художественный образ, подробность*

One of the key active components in a literary text, in terms of its functionality, is often the artistic minutiae, which is elevated to the level of the artistic image. According to A.B. Yesenin, "...as a part of the artistic whole, the artistic minutiae are, in itself, small images, micro-images. At the same time, the minutiae almost always form a part of a larger depiction..." (3, p. 49). In some cases, artistic minutiae is equated with the concept of detail, while in other cases, they are distinguished. In his article "Artistic Minutiae and Detail", linguist Kamil Valiyev writes: "Minutiae is such a part of the detail that through it, the artistic description enhances its light, and the chain reaction of associations reveals different shades. Here, on the contrary, the role of the minutiae in reflecting the detail should be revealed" (11, p. 108). Critic Nargiz Abdullayeva (Cab-

barli), who highly evaluates the place and role of artistic minutiae in contemporary poetry, writes: "The minutiae directs the reader's attention to what is significant for the writer-such as the colors of a landscape that could be a key to a specific meaning, a situation, or the most important aspects of human character, environment, appearance, and psychological state. Sometimes, it is precisely through some artistic minutiae that the reader obtains as much important information as a large piece of text can provide. (1, p. 232).

There are various types of artistic minutiae, such as psychological minutiae, visual minutiae, landscape minutiae, symbolic minutiae and so on. Symbolic minutiae can be divided into several groups. Symbolic minutiae that create a portrait, symbolic minutiae that depict the psychological state of the lyrical hero, symbolic

minutiae that give a visual appearance to the event and situation.

Symbolic minutiae are of particular importance in creating a portrait of the lyrical hero, in characterizing his emotional and psychological state, and as an artistic definition of his inner essence.

Otuzdan çox yaşamışam...

Bəzən baş tutmayan şeirim

Dağılmış divarlarının xarabasında,

Bəzən söz yarışında.

Bəzən ölüm sözünün polyar qışında.... (4, s.5).

“I have lived for more than thirty years...

Sometimes in the ruins of my failed poetry,

Sometimes in the competition of words,

Sometimes in the polar winter of the word death...” (4, p. 5).

The symbolic function of the minutiae is complex. In fact, artistic minutiae has no function in isolation. The sign existing in the substratum of memory can create symbolic content, an image for the author's idea. Although the image itself has a direct symbolic content, it has a more effective impact based on the artistic minutiae in memory.

Göyə baxdım,

birəm-birəm qar gəlir.

Kərəm düşdü yadıma,

Əfsanələrin ən gözəllərindən:

iki məzar,

arada bir qaratikan kolu,

Ax, bu kollar, bu kollar:

Hər zaman

İşimizə, gücümüzə əngəl olurlar (10, s.235)..

I looked at the sky,

The snowflakes were falling one by one.

Kerem came to my mind,

Two graves from one of the most beautiful of legends:

Between them, a thorn bush,

Ah, these bushes, these bushes:

They always obstruct our work, our strength... (10, p. 235).

The word used as artistic minutiae fills the text with new meanings, the minutiae turns into an artistic image. In Ali Kerim's poem “Babek's arms”, Babek's arms are symbolic minutiae. Sometimes, the text arises from the confluence of several poetic categories, and at such moments, defining boundaries creates difficulties. In A. Kerim's poem “Babek's arms”, the struggle of the hero's severed arms is depicted. After a certain time, the function of the artistic minutiae deepens, becomes metaphorical, the semantic load of the text expands, turns into a symbol, delving into deeper layers of artistic thought, becomes a continuation of the moral responsibility of both yesterday, today and the future. However, this deepening does not harm the status of the minutiae.

Qolu sındırılmış Babək;

Yurdu yandırılmış Babək,

Qan rəngli bir arabada,

Şərq boyda bir xarabada,

Söyə-söyə,

Döyə-döyə,

Hamıya görk olsun deyə

Kənd-kənd gəzdirilən Babək,

Ölübən dirilən Babək...

Bir qırmızı yuxu içrə,

Uzaqlara dalan Babək.

Deyən Babək: -Aman dostlar,

Hücum çəkin qoşun-qoşun

Orda mənsiz qılınc çalan

Qollarımla bir vuruşun. (4, s.18).

Babek with broken arms;

Babek with his homeland burned,

In a blood-colored cart,

In a ruin as vast as the East,

Beaten and abused,

Babek who was taken from village to village,

To be seen by all,

Babek who was resurrected from the dead...

In a red dream,

Drifted to the distance,

Babek said: - Oh, friends,

Attack with troops,

Fight with my arms,

That rattles sabre without me. (4, p. 18).

In Rasul Rza's poem “My Acquaintance with non-existence”, the image and description determine the psychological mood in an expressive-emotional form.

Əvvəlcə yavaşdan çağırdım,

Sonra ucadan

Ay ev yiyəsi!

Ev susdu

Qapılar susdu

Neçə yerdə sökülmüş

Batdaq divar susdu,

Qanrılıb bir də baxdım.

Hər yer tanışdı.

Həyətə gedən,

üstünü ot basmış

cığırdan başqa (9, s.259).

At first, I called quietly,

Then loudly,

Oh, master of the house!

The house fell silent,

The doors fell silent,

The wall, demolished in places, was silent,

I looked again, confused.

Everywhere was familiar.

Except for the path leading to the yard,

The path overgrown with grass (9, p. 259).

The entire weight of the artistic text is centered on the symbolic minutiae of the “path overgrown with grass”. Regardless of where the symbolic minutiae appear in any part of the text, it determines both the entry and exit points in that text. All developments are summarized in the content of specific minutiae. Symbolic minutiae were widely used in Azerbaijani poetry of the 1920s-60s. The possibilities of symbolic minutiae in giving a visual appearance to an artistic image and in creating a portrait are wide. In Rasul Rza's poem “*Bal-lad about the Negro Child Willie*”, the goal is not only to create a portrait of the Negro child **Willie** through

symbolic minutiae but also to reveal the essence of the situation by using symbolic minutiae, to reflect the image more clearly and concretely, while also giving a poetic tonal quality to the image and delving into the depths of the essence.

Səhər...
 Üfüqdə qan ləkəsi
 Daxma qabağında quru budaq kölgəsi,
 Kölgə - zənci balası Villidir.
 Yerdə bir qara yumaq,
 Bir də quru budaq kölgəsi.
 Gilə-gilə qırmızı düymələr
 dağılıb hər yana
 Ağköynək üstünə,
 saçlara,
 qara dodaqlar arasına (9, s.154).

Morning...

A bloodstain on the horizon

**A shadow of a dry branch in front of the hut,
 The shadow is Willie, the Negro child.**

A black ball on the ground,
 And the shadow of the dry branch
 Red buttons scattered all around,
 In the hair,
 On the white shirt,
 And between the black lips (9, p.154).

The artistic minutiae used in depicting the merciless death of the colored schoolboy **Willie** – “shadow”, “the shadow of a dry branch”, and the red buttons scattered everywhere on the white shirt, hair, and between the black lips – not only increase the dramatic effect of the event but also enhance its expressiveness.

The minutiae carry an idea to some extent. In the analysis of artistic minutiae, is often categorized into several groups. A.B. Yesin writes: “For an easy analysis of artistic minutiae, it can be divided into several groups. Firstly, minutiae are divided into external and psychological categories” (3, p.48). The researcher initially divides the minutiae into two categories and further into several parts.

In the analysis of artistic detail, it is divided into several groups. A.B. Yesin writes: “For convenient analysis of artistic detail, it can be divided into several groups. Firstly, the minutiae is divided into external and psychological groups” (3, p. 48). The researcher divides the minutiae that he initially divided into two groups into several parts. He divides external minutiae into three parts: portrait, landscape and object categories. Psychological minutiae, on the other hand, play an important role in representing the psychological world of the individual, revealing the realm of feelings and thoughts. The creation of such minutiae also highlights the difference between artistic minutiae and detail. In external characterization the detail is more pronounced, while in the second group, the function of the minutiae is more characteristic. This is where distinctions between minutiae, detail, and symbol emerge. Thus, the detail is functional in the formation of the symbol and is the basis for its understanding and creation. Although some researchers argue that the minutiae and the detail are the same, some researchers note that they are different from each other. A.V. Yesin distinguishes between

minutiae and detail-symbol from the viewpoint of artistic impact. He writes: “Minutiae move in mass, depicting an object or event from all sides, while the symbolic detail is singular, trying to capture the essence of the event, highlighting the core element” (3, p.50).

Literary scholar E. Dobin also distinguishes between minutiae and details, noting that the artistic value of detail is superior to minutiae (though not everyone agrees with this view - G.Q). He writes: “Detail operates in the aggregate. Minutiae tend toward individuality... There is no absolute distinction between artistic detail and minutiae. There are transitional forms and connecting stages between them”.(2, p.304-305). The creation of an impression about any event, situation, portrait, or landscape through certain minutiae brought to the image by the author is given as artistic minutiae, including detail. If minutiae chosen in a literary text for psychological or philosophical typification, acquires a certain idea or associative content, it becomes symbolic. Symbolic minutiae are not widespread but are functional around specific minutiae and are subordinated to the idea. The scholarly exploration of the function of artistic minutiae in the text, as well as the scientific and theoretical resolution of the similarities and differences between detail and minutiae is also of interest in the scientific postulates put forward by N.Abdulayeva. Noting that there is not a significant difference between minutiae and detail, and that the boundary between them is minimal, the literary scholar develops his ideas, noting that there is a certain difference within this similarity itself, and writes: “By detail, most scholars mean extensive minutiae that cannot be distinguished, especially those that do not have the property of being symbolized, and that do not turn into a complete artistic image. That is, a detail is an extensive minutiae that does not symbolize, or, conversely, an intensive-quality detail that can turn into a symbol is called minutiae”. (1, p.233). It should also be noted that the concept of detail inherently carries the idea of an informational collective. In other words, detail is a specific text, and inside it, there may or may not be an artistic minutiae. The specific expression within the status text becomes individualized as artistic minutiae, and the character of these minutiae finds confirmation within the whole text. Emphasizing and visualizing a particular feature of the character’s image, psychological state, or situation is a characteristic feature of symbolic minutiae. M. Mushfig extensively used symbolic minutiae when embodying the poetic image of the drunkard.

Alnında bir bəyaz qəm, - bir dilənçi günündə -
 Üzü günəşdən qızıl, içi qarlardan ağdır (8, s.39).

A white sorrow on the forehead, - on a beggar’s day -

The face is golden from the sun, the inside is white from snow (8, p.39).

Even the smallest minutiae in the text can be transformed into an image and symbolized. In such cases, the artistic minutiae carry an endless meaning; gather all its components around itself, and direct attention to the expression of larger ideas within the context of the content of the chosen minutiae. In R. Rza’s “The Fragile Branch”, M. Araz’s “The crutch”,

and Qabil's "Straw Stick" poems, the symbolic minutiae such as "the fragile branch", "the crutch", and "the yellow straw stick" play a significant role in revealing the ideology of the artistic text. In R.Rza's poem "The Fragile Branch", the fragile branch, which grows from the trunk and blooms with buds and young leaves, becomes symbolic throughout the poem, acquiring new meanings. The breaking of the simple branch due to the touch of trembling hands or the fear of the harsh wind, the permanent wound left on the trunk, and the visible scar makes the reader ponder over. Minutiae scattered throughout the plot only create a certain impression, while a symbolic minutiae is ideological, functional, and associative.

Saman çöpü
Yaxamdan əl çəkib saçlarıma qondu,
Saçlarım, aman allah,
Bəmbəyaz qara döndü.
Büküldü belim
Əsa axtardı əlim.
Əlimə saman çöpü keçdi sapsarı.
Saman çöpüylə axıb damarıma calandı,
Elektrik cərəyanları,
Şimşəklər bürüdü cismimi (6, s.106).

Straw Stick

It left my collar and landed on my hair,
My hair, oh my god,
Turned black as pitch.
My back bent,
My hand searched for a cane.
A yellow straw stick passed into my hand.
With the straw stick flowing through my veins,
Electric currents,
Lightning covered my body. (6, p.106)

The yellow straw stick, flying from the palm and landing on the collar or hair, sometimes becomes a symbol of clarity, purity, truth, and labor, and at other times, it takes on contradictory functions, such as the tip of a double-edged dagger or a golden snake. Thus, it transforms into a symbolic image of a person who, "grasping the straw stick, fighting along the way," represents the struggles and hardships of life.

The symbolic transformation of artistic minutiae does not always occur. Minutiae can either become symbolic or remain non-symbolic. Symbolic minutiae are distinguished by their functionality when portraying the inner psychological state of the lyrical hero. A symbol is a broader concept in terms of content. It stands whole, with a strong tendency to generalize. In symbolic minutiae, however, the essence of a particular situation, event, or circumstance is revealed and given meaning. Artistic minutiae perform a supporting role in the text and are functional in all aspects. The creation of a portrait, the detailed depiction of nature in alignment with a specific idea, the psychological configuration of the events unfolding throughout the plot, and the substantiation of the author's inner psychological state in accordance with a particular situation all gain artistic specificity through the functionality of artistic minutiae.

Qopdu bir ömür də öz budağından
Qopdu saralmamış bir yarpaq kimi (7, s.109).

One life torn away from its branch Like a leaf not yet yellowed (7, p.109).

The early psychological shade of death is concretized in the artistic minutiae of "a leaf not yet turned yellow", becoming the basis for the emotional expression of the idea.

What distinguishes artistic minutiae is its concreteness. Details are more extensive and comprehensive; they can have the function of providing specific information, descriptions, visual clarity, portraits, or character creation. In comparison, the possibilities of artistic minutiae, especially symbolic ones, are limited but more substantial. The meaning, associations, and logic of a symbol are well-established. It remains connected to the original meaning of a particular image, regardless of time and place, and does not lose its relevance. In another context, it can be repeated, but its function may not be the same for every image or minutiae. Artistic minutiae are a small component of the text, often intense and functional in revealing the idea. Through the minutiae -symbol, the general psychological state can be identified, the author's attitude towards the depicted moment can be clearly expressed, and certain aspects of the character, depiction, event, or situation can be typified, helping to clarify the poet's intention and main idea. This can be clearly demonstrated in the poems by M. Araz "Azerbaijan, My Homeland" and by Q. Qasimzadeh "The Violet Leaf".

Azərbaycan, qayalarda bitən bir çiçək,
Azərbaycan, çiçəklər içərisində, qaya (7, s. 100).

Azerbaijan, a flower growing on rocks, Azerbaijan, a rock among flowers (7, p.100).

The smallest components of the poem, the flower and the rock, are concrete artistic minutiae. They are original minutiae in terms of generalizing the artistic image and providing a clear expression of the poet's thoughts. The hidden meaning is not characteristic for artistic minutiae. When minutiae become symbolic, it can acquire special, non-ordinary meanings, reflecting the psychological state, desires, wishes, thoughts, and reflections of the lyrical self. This, in turn, provides the creative individual with the opportunity to poetically shape any artistic minutiae according to their will, turning it from ordinary minutiae into a symbol.

In N. Kesemenli's poem, the artistic minutiae of "kissing the forehead" as a symbolic minutiae represent a death ritual, a moment of separation, an irreversible journey, and the last meeting with loved ones.

Hər axşam qaralan günün
Alnından öpdü gözüm,
Alnından öpdüklərim bir də dönmədi geri....
Bir gün babamın alnından öpdük
Əvvəl nənəm, sonra mən:
Bir gün də nənəmin alnından öpdük,
Əvvəl anam, sonra mən;
Sonra anamın alnından öpdük,
Əvvəl ölüm, sonra mən... (5, s.36-37)

Every evening, as the day darkens, My eyes kissed the forehead, The ones I kissed on the forehead never returned...

**One day, we kissed my grandfather's forehead,
First my grandmother, then me;
One day, we kissed my grandmother's forehead,
First my mother, then me;
Then we kissed my mother's forehead,
First death, then me...** (5, p.36-37)

Thus, the characteristic that brings artistic minutiae closer to symbolism is the quality it acquires after it becomes symbolic. The author can use as many artistic minutiae as needed in the text. This is both a necessity and a specific feature of the minutiae. However, the symbol is singular in the text, and it tends to concentrate all meanings around it. Through artistic minutiae, the psychological state of the hero, their outward appearance and features, and the "visualization of the image" can be enhanced, and the details of the event or situation are revealed and given meaning. As a factual reality, there is no hidden moment for it. However, a symbol points to an additional meaning beyond the primary one. The moment that brings minutiae closer to symbolism is when both come together in the text, and they need each other. When minutiae become symbolic, it moves away from its literal meaning and creates real opportunities for the author to reveal the idea and content to the reader.

References

1. Abdullayeva N. Çağdaş Azərbaycan şeirinin bədii ifadə sistemində poetik detalların rolu. //Poetika.izm. Bakı, Elm və Təhsil, 2014 №1, səh.232-245
2. Добин Е. Сюжет и действительность; Искусство детали / Е. Добин. - Л.: Сов. писатель, 1981, 432 с
3. Есин А.Б. Принципы и методы анализа литературного произведения. М.: Флинта.Наукв. 2000, 286 с
4. Kərim Əli. Seçilmiş əsərləri. 2 cildə, I c., Bakı, Azərnəşr, 1991, 272 s
5. Kəsəmənli Nüsrət. Hamısı sevgidəndir. Bakı, Gənclik, 1991, 296 s
6. Qabil. Təmizlik. Şeirlər və poemalar. Bakı, Yazıçı, 1983, 116 s.
7. Məmməd Araz. Seçilmiş əsərləri. İki cildə, I c., Bakı, "Lider nəşriyyat", 2004, 224 s
8. Mikayıl Müşfiq. Həyat sevgisi. Bakı, Yazıçı, 1988, 304 s
9. Rza Rəsul. Seçilmiş əsərləri. V cildə, I c., Bakı, Azərnəşr, 457 s
10. Rza Rəsul. Seçilmiş əsərləri, Beş cildə, II c., Bakı, "Öndər nəşriyyatı", 2005, 320 s
11. Vəliyev, K. Bədii detal və təfərrüat //K.Vəliyev. Sözlün sehri. – Bakı: – Yazıçı. – 1986. – 106 s.